

Sustainable Care, Lasting Impact

Living with chronic kidney disease (CKD) means facing unique challenges, including environmental ones.

Did you know that kidney care generates waste, uses water and energy, emits travel-related carbon and therefore strains the environment?

KitNewCare is introducing innovative treatments and prevention strategies to reduce resource use and environmental impact.

Join KitNewCare and be part of the **healthcare** **revolution**

KitNewCare, an EU-funded project, aims to revolutionise kidney care for a sustainable and carbon-neutral future.

It will pilot and implement the following technological innovations:

Water treatment advancements for dialysis

aiming for minimal water consumption, by reusing waste streams and applying forward osmosis for dialysate production.

Energy-efficient technologies

to use renewable resources and reduce energy consumption, by implementing solar-assisted dialysis and heat exchangers for dialysate warming.

Waste reduction technologies to minimise (biohazardous) waste generation, by using dry powder acid concentrate with centralised distribution systems and dialyser reprocessing systems.

KitNewCare empowers healthcare professionals with the latest tools and knowledge in kidney care.

Together, we can enhance patient outcomes and build a healthier, more sustainable future.

The innovative solutions developed by KitNewCare include:

Benchmarking tool and dashboard to record impacts in healthcare.

4-factor life cycle assessment database to measure social, environmental, financial and health factors.

Training modules to empower professionals with essential green skills and practices.

Guidelines and recommendations to provide a roadmap for sustainable kidney care.

Set of workflow optimisations and technical innovations to promote sustainable care.

Learn how to better manage CKD and contribute to a greener future while maintaining the same care standards.

Take charge of your health by making informed decisions about CKD. Visit our website for comprehensive information and resources, including links to hospitals and renal centres and a wealth of supporting literature.

www.kitnewcare.eu

Contact us at
info@kitnewcare.eu

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